

Master thesis on Computational Musical Creativity
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Tap2Drum with Transformer Neural Networks

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Dedication

To my lovely Elisabeth, I miss you.

A lot.

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Y a mis padres y mi hermano, lo que más quiero en este mundo: gracias por todo.

Abstract

In a paper recently published by the Google Magenta team, in the context of automatic beat generation and beat humanization, a new task called Tap2Drum is described. In this task, the aim is to transform a tapped pattern into a full-fledged drum beat. This master thesis implements, trains and evaluates a Transformer Neural Network model for Tap2Drum beat generation, motivated by the creative possibilities of such a system for musicians and producers. The dataset used for training, as in our baseline (GrooVAE Seq2Seq), is the Groove MIDI Dataset. Several experiments have been carried out, of which the best models have been selected to be evaluated. The evaluation performed consists of a mixture of objective metrics and subjective observations based on our personal listening sessions. According to said evaluation, our model achieves competitive results, comparable to those of our baseline, although we cannot definitively claim it performs better.

Keywords: drum pattern generation, beat generation, tap2drum, symbolic music generation

Chapter 1

Introduction

Most of us probably possess more musical knowledge than we realize. Just by listening to music, an undeniably big part of human culture, we have learned patterns, combinations of sounds and sequences that sound good to us or make us feel something. Even though listening to and appreciating music is something so universal, generating it is less so – the skills required to create a song, ranging from mastering a musical instrument to becoming proficient in the use of Digital Audio Workstations (DAWs) can take a lot of dedication and effort, discouraging many in the process.

Computational approaches to generative music and assisted composition techniques could aid those of us that are less trained in the matter, helping to make musical ideas come to life, and those that are already skilled could experiment with new tools for musical creation.

This master thesis focuses on a task called “Tap2Drum”, first described in [1]. This task consists of transforming a sequence of *taps* into a full drum pattern, allowing the generation of complex beats from a significantly simpler musical abstraction, as illustrated in Figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1: Single-tapped sequence to full drum beat (Tap2Drum)

1.1 Related work

Algorithmic music generation has been around for a long time. Methods to compose music using sets of rules, randomness, probability distributions or a combination of these approaches have been used long before the computer era [2]. Nonetheless, the development of computers and their increasing calculation power opened the doors to new composition methods that before were only possible in theory. [3] and [4] are good examples of early meaningful works that started to delve into this world of computational musical creativity.

1.1.1 Deep Learning in generative music

Deep Learning (DL) algorithms train models to perform specific tasks by feeding them data in the form of inputs and outputs and allowing the models to implicitly learn how to get from one to the other. Consequently, the performance of these algorithms depends not only in the models' architecture but also in the quality, quantity and nature of the data these models are trained on. Music consists of sounds, rests and combinations of sounds over time, and naturally, the order in which they happen is very important. This sequential essence has a very high impact on how DL models deal with music data, especially on generative tasks.

Some architectures are not compatible with sequential tasks, for instance, Vanilla¹

¹In the context of Machine Learning and Deep Learning, this term is generally used to refer to the most basic, stripped-down and unmodified implementation of something.

Neural Networks (NN) allow data to travel through the model in one direction only: input to output. However, music generation requires a system capable of recursively reusing its outputs as input, so that, for example, a generated note in a melody would affect the notes to follow.

Recurrent Neural Networks

One of the first NN models able to process information in a sequential manner, making it suitable for generative music, is the Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) architecture. RNNs persist the state of nodes in the hidden layer, creating a sort of memory. In Figure 1.2, a vanilla NN is illustrated along with a RNN. As can be seen in said figure, a RNN can be represented as a chain of identical NNs, using one NN per sequential element of the input (3 in this representation).

Figure 1.2: Simplified representation of a vanilla Artificial Neural Network architecture and a Recurrent Neural Network architecture

RNNs have been used for music composition as early as 1989 [5], with some success generating short sequences of melodies. Nevertheless, both [5] and later [6] in 1994 outline the main limitation of this architecture: lack of long term memory. RNNs

are really good at learning short term structure, but when sequences get longer, the gradient² either vanishes or explodes, hindering the system from learning any further. Moreover, the computations in RNNs are carried out sequentially, and as the sequence gets longer, the computational cost increases greatly.

Long Short-Term Memory

To solve the vanishing gradient problem, later works came up with solutions such as the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) [7] or Gate Recurrent Unit (GRU) mechanisms. These would control whether previous information is remembered (propagated forward) or forgotten. Both LSTMs and GRUs use gates to manage memory. Figure 1.3 shows the inner workings of an LSTM cell: a system state and a memory vector coming from the previous node activate or not the ‘forget’ gate, allowing the model to manage which part of the state to leave behind. The ‘input’ gate decides what new information to propagate forward and the ‘output’ gate decides what to output taking into account the cell state.

Figure 1.3: A hidden node of an LSTM-RNN, representing the gating mechanism.

The first experiment that learned longer-term structures and replicated them using this mechanism was carried out in [8], where an LSTM-RNN learned the musical chord structure of a 12-bar blues successfully. Another interesting experiment was

²Gradient descent is one of the methods used to find the optimal parameters of a model, i.e., the way the model learns.

carried out in [9], where word- and character-based RNNs with LSTM units were employed to generate jazz chord progressions and rock drum tracks, using text-only representations of music data as inputs. Word-RNNs reportedly succeeded in both tasks, whereas char-RNNs failed to produce good results for the drum track generation task.

Additionally, an interesting proposal in [10] combined an LSTM-RNN module and a Feed Forward NN for conditional rhythm composition, where the LSTM learned drum patterns and generation, while the Feed Forward NN learned meter and bass guitar features to condition the rhythm generation.

There are a number of variants of LSTM architectures, refined and modified for different tasks and experiments: Bidirectional LSTM-RNN models are applied in [11] for chord progression generation, and in [12] for rhythm, chord and melody generation, while [13] and [14] explore the use of Biaxial LSTMs for polyphonic music generation. In [15], a novel architecture called Anticipation-RNN is proposed, implementing a system for interactive melody generation based on LSTM-RNNs.

Variational AutoEncoders

AutoEncoders (AEs) are models built to reconstruct high-dimensional data from a lower-dimensional trained representation, typically built from RNNs or LSTM-RNNs. Figure 1.4a shows a high level overview of an AE: there are two main components, an encoder and a decoder. The bottleneck in the middle forces the encoder to compress the data into a latent vector z , making the decoder then attempt to reconstruct as best as possible the input from that compressed representation. After reconstruction, the system can compare how similar the output is to the input. No supervision is required since the system can use the error between the output and the input sequences as a performance metric.

Figure 1.4b illustrates a modified version of an AE called Variational AutoEncoder (VAE). Instead of learning a compressed representation in the form of a vector, VAEs learn a distribution represented by its mean and standard deviation. This can then be used to generate new sequences by sampling from the learned distribution and

(a) AutoEncoder (AE)

(b) Variational AutoEncoder (VAE)

Figure 1.4: High-level representations of AutoEncoder architectures.

feeding this sample into the decoder.

The MusicVAE model ([16], [17]) uses a recurrent VAE architecture and a hierarchical decoder to generate music with improved long-term structure. The latent space representation of musical information makes possible different transformations on the low dimensional data that can then generate new high-dimensional musical sequences.

Sequence to sequence models

Sequence to sequence (Seq2Seq) models also have encoder-decoder structures, but rather than being concerned with a latent lower-dimensional representation, they focus on generating a sequence from another. There is still a sequence at the beginning and end, but now the output sequence is different from the input one. The simplest example of an application would be a system carrying out machine translation, e.g. receiving a natural language sequence in English as input and generating

an equivalent sentence in French. The encoder captures the context of the input in a hidden state vector and sends it to the decoder, which uses this context to generate the new sequence. Many of these systems are based on LSTM-RNNs, propagating the hidden state vector and the cell state from one unit to the next, as shown in Figure 1.5 (also note that the output from the encoder is not as important as in VAEs).

Figure 1.5: Seq2seq LSTM-RNN architecture overview.

In [18], a Seq2Seq model is used to generate a full drum beat (output) from a kick drum pattern (input) in specific styles with moderate success. The paper ([1]) in which most of this master thesis is based, uses a Seq2Seq architecture to perform two novel tasks: InFilling and Tap2Drum. In InFilling, the goal is to generate a full drum beat from for a given pattern that is somewhat incomplete (voices have been removed), *filling in* the beat with missing instruments, whereas in Tap2Drum, the objective is to generate a full drum beat from a very reduced abstraction: a tapped sequence. Also in [1], the Groove MIDI Dataset (GMD) is presented, a symbolic dataset with drum performances, which is used to train Seq2Seq models to perform the two previously mentioned tasks, showing competitive and promising results.

Transformers

Many of the models described have been adapted from the field of Natural Language Processing (NLP) since music and language share a sequential nature. Both for NLP and music generation, Seq2Seq models based on LSTM are better than some of the prior proposals. LSTMs allow for longer sequence generation, but they still have a limited memory. In 2017, [19] proposed to solve this problem and get rid of recurrence by using the so-called ‘Attention’ mechanism. Attention is the idea that different elements in a sequence *attend* more to other specific elements in the sequence. In DL, attention could be described as a vector or set of importance weights that is used when inferring an element in a sequence to determine how strongly it correlates to the other elements in said sequence. The architecture proposed in [19] is called Transformer, and uses an encoder, a decoder and a particular attention mechanism called multi-head self-attention. In Chapter 2 the vanilla Transformer architecture is further discussed as it is the methodology employed in this master thesis.

Transformer NNs have become a popular approach to sequential data processing in the past few years, delivering promising results in music generation tasks. In [20], the Music Transformer is presented, a proposal for a long-term structure music generation system. In it, the vanilla Transformer is modified by incorporating a variation on the attention mechanism called relative attention, that encodes in the attention scores how far two positions in the sequence are from one another. This model obtained very competitive results in listening tests, outperforming LSTMs and vanilla Transformers.

[21] and [22] both use Transformer-XL architectures, a model that brings the notion of recurrence back, combining it with Transformers. The Pop Music Transformer, a Transformer-XL model proposed in [21], is trained on music data in a novel format called REMI (REvamped MIDI-derived events), and claims to outperform the Music Transformer ([20]) in the generation of expressive Pop piano compositions. In [22], on the other hand, the Transformer-XL is trained on the Groove MIDI dataset [1] for the tasks of drum sequences generation and continuation. Listening test results

show that this model performs better than the baseline Seq2Seq.

1.2 Goals

The aim of this master thesis is to implement and evaluate a Transformer NN model for the task of Tap2Drum described in [1], competing, if not outperforming, our baseline.

Tap2Drum, by generating more complex drum beat sequences from simpler ones has great potential in helping producers, musicians and music enthusiasts alike in their beat creation journeys.

Chapter 2

Methodology

In this project, a vanilla Transformer NN is implemented and trained. The dataset used and its processing, the chosen model architecture and hyperparameter tuning will be described in this chapter. You can find our code repository [here](#)¹, also linked in Appendix A.

2.1 Groove MIDI Dataset

The model is trained using Magenta’s Groove MIDI Dataset (GMD)[1], a dataset containing roughly 13.6 hours of drum performances in the format of beats and fills, classified by genre and mostly in 4/4 time signature.

Seeing that the dataset is already divided in train ($\sim 80\%$), test ($\sim 10\%$) and validation ($\sim 10\%$) subsets, the experiments are conducted using these partitions. The training is done exclusively with beats (none of the fills are used) and 4/4 examples. Furthermore, the examples are split into two measure beats, ending up with the dataset size shown in Table 2.1.

Although there are 16 different genres available, as can be seen in Figure 2.1, of all the 4/4 beat examples more than half the examples belong to only 3 of those genres. This means that the trained models will probably be biased towards those genres.

¹<https://github.com/marinaniet0/TransformerGrooveTap2Drum>

Split	Beats	Examples (2-measure length)
Train	378	16195
Test	77	2054
Validation	48	2021
Total	503	20270

Table 2.1: Number of examples per subset of the GMD. 2-measure length examples are all 4/4 beats.

Figure 2.1: Genre distribution in the GMD (4/4, beats only)

2.1.1 Data representation

To prepare the data to feed the model, a series of transformations are performed on the original MIDI files. As in [1], the drum kit instruments are reduced and mapped to a smaller set. The MIDI drum classes defined in the General MIDI Standard are mapped to 9 instruments or voices, as shown in Table 2.2.

The data is then converted from MIDI format to a vector representation to be able to feed it to the model². This vector representation, that will be labeled HVO from now on (Hits, Velocities, Offsets), is the same being used in [1], and consists of a

²The following repository provides functions to do all the preprocessing necessary: https://github.com/behzadhaki/hvo_sequence

Drum voice	General MIDI note numbers
Kick	36
Snare	38, 37, 40
Closed Hi-Hat	42, 22, 44
Open Hi-Hat	46, 26
Low Tom	43, 58
Mid Tom	47, 45
High Tom	50, 48
Crash	49, 52, 55, 57
Ride	51, 53, 59

Table 2.2: Reduced drum mapping

matrix of dimensions $m \times n$, where m represents the number of timesteps and n the number of voices times 3 (since we are representing 3 aspects of each time event and voice - hits, velocities and offsets).

In order to represent time as a vector, a grid is applied with a resolution of 4 timesteps per beat. Since only 4/4 2-measure examples are being taken and the reduced drum mapping used has 9 voices, the matrices used in these experiments will always have dimensions 32×27 .

In Table 2.3 an example of this data representation is shown. Hit values can only be 1 or 0, meaning at that timestep, that particular voice is activated (1) or not (0). Velocities are represented as float numbers ranging from 0 to 1, indicating how hard that hit is being played. Lastly, offsets, ranging from -0.5 to 0.5, depict how far from the grid that specific hit is, where 0 means the hit starts exactly on the grid line.

	Hits				Velocities				Offsets			
	kick	snare	closed hat	...	kick	snare	closed hat	...	kick	snare	closed hat	...
1	1	0	1		0.59	0	0.61		-0.05	0	-0.08	
2	0	0	0	...	0	0	0	...	0	0	0	...
3	0	1	1		0	0.7	0.43		0	0.2	0.18	
	⋮				⋮				⋮			
32	0	0	1	...	0	0	0.38	...	0	0	-0.1	...

Table 2.3: HVO representation example (showing only 3 of the 9 drum voices)

Tapped sequence

In order to have tapped input sequences, the original patterns are transformed into a single voice sequence. This is done in the same manner as in [1], *squeezing* all voices onto a single one (see Figure 2.2). If there is more than one hit at a single timestep, the velocity and offset values of the hit with highest velocity are kept.

Figure 2.2: Drum pattern being *squeezed* into a single-voice or tapped sequence

2.1.2 Direct embedding

Since Transformers originally appeared in the NLP field, tokenization is almost always used with this architecture, seeing that words need to be transformed into vectors before being fed to the model. These tokens or embeddings are learned, which means there is an additional task for the model to perform - representing a large vocabulary of words and their semantics with vectors. However, the *vocabulary* used in this project only has 9 elements. Considering the simplicity with which different events in a beat can be represented with HVOs and the relatively small size of the GMD, no tokenization will be used, proving whether or not tokenization is really necessary when using Transformers for generative (symbolic) music tasks.

2.2 Architecture

An overview of the Transformer architecture employed³ is shown in Figure 2.3. The tapped sequences as HVO matrices are passed through a linear layer, mapping it to a different dimension (`d_model`), e.g. from 27 to 64 values per timestep.

Figure 2.3: Overview of model architecture

Then, an encoding is applied to preserve temporal information as proposed by [19]. This is necessary because attention scores are computed on each timestep individually, losing the sequential context. When the positional encoding vector is added to an input sequence, each individual timestep now carries information about where it

³The code for our model architecture including training and prediction scripts can be found at <https://github.com/behzadhaki/BaseGrooveTransformers>

is located within the sequence. It is calculated using a combination of a sine and cosine function following Equation 2.1.

$$\begin{aligned} PE_{(pos,2i)} &= \sin\left(\frac{pos}{10000^{2i/d_{model}}}\right) \\ PE_{(pos,2i+1)} &= \cos\left(\frac{pos}{10000^{2i/d_{model}}}\right) \end{aligned} \tag{2.1}$$

Afterwards, the data passes through a Transformer encoder, which is comprised of several layers, each of them composed by a multi-head attention module and a feedforward NN. The multi-head attention module uses several (`n_heads`) parallel attention mechanisms, learning how each part of the beat attends to other parts, that is, how relevant each timestep is to each other timestep. The feedforward NN then processes the data that now includes attention information and generates an output, which is then passed through another linear layer. If the model is in training mode, the velocities and offsets pass through a sigmoid and hyperbolic tangent respectively. Then, from the generated hits, velocities and offsets a loss value is calculated for backpropagation of the gradient of the total loss. If, on the contrary, the model is in prediction mode, all three generated matrices go through their corresponding activation functions.

2.2.1 Losses and multitask learning

During training, the loss value used to backpropagate and learn is a linear combination of three loss values. These three loss values correspond to a Binary Cross Entropy loss (BCE) for the hits, a Mean Squared Error (MSE) loss for the velocities and another MSE for the offsets. In the ground truth HVOs there are more zeros than other values - not all timesteps have events, and rarely more than 3 voices are activated at once. In order to help the model give more importance to those losses where the expected hits are 1, a *penalty* or multiplying factor p that ranges from 0 to 1 is applied to the hit, velocity and offset loss values where the expected hits are 0. These calculations are detailed in Equation 2.2.

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{loss} &= \text{hit loss} + \text{velocity loss} + \text{offset loss} \\
\text{hit loss} &= \sum_{i,j} (\mathbf{P} \circ \text{BCE}(\mathbf{H}_{\text{predicted}}, \mathbf{H}_{\text{expected}}))_{i,j} \\
\text{velocity loss} &= \sum_{i,j} (\mathbf{P} \circ \text{MSE}(\mathbf{V}_{\text{predicted}}, \mathbf{V}_{\text{expected}}))_{i,j} \\
\text{offset loss} &= \sum_{i,j} (\mathbf{P} \circ \text{MSE}(\mathbf{O}_{\text{predicted}}, \mathbf{O}_{\text{expected}}))_{i,j} \\
\mathbf{P} &= p \cdot (\mathbf{J} - \mathbf{H}_{\text{expected}}), \quad 0 \leq p \leq 1
\end{aligned} \tag{2.2}$$

$$\mathbf{J} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

2.3 Hyperparameter tuning

A considerable amount of hyperparameters need to be chosen in order to configure the Transformer model:

- Batch size: number of examples that go through a learning iteration together.
- d_{model} : dimension to which the inputs will be mapped to when going through the first linear layer.
- Feedforward NN dimension: size of the feedforward neural network located in each layer of the transformer.
- Dropout value: during training, probability of an element of the network to be zeroed. This helps the model to not overfit, since not all connections are working on every training run, as proposed in [23].
- Optimizer algorithm: algorithm that will be used to update the parameters of the model when doing backpropagation, e.g. Stochastic Gradient Descent

(SGD).

- Learning rate: step size for each learning iteration towards minima of the loss values.
- Loss penalty multiplier or p : value from 0 to 1, applied to the losses of predictions where there are no hits in the expected values, so the model prioritizes learning those values where hits are located. See p in Equation 2.2.
- Number of heads: number of heads in the multihead attention mechanism.
- Number of layers: number of transformer layers, each composed by a multihead attention module and a feedforward NN.

It is a challenging task to tune these hyperparameters looking at values used for similar architectures or tasks, since there are multitude of combinations that could be tested and perhaps none of them would work for this specific case. However, with the help of the library and API provided by Weights and Biases (W&B) [24] this process becomes easier. W&B provides the functionality to define ranges, distributions or sets of values for each of the tunable parameters and *sweep* through them, observing which combinations of parameters result in a lower loss value, for example.

Figure 2.4: Example sweep with 12 runs and 7 hyperparameters.

In Figure 2.4 an example sweep is shown, where each line represents a training run with each of the parameters the line passes through. The loss value of the last iteration of each run is shown on the right bar. W&B's API can also be used to keep track of different values and media elements during training, allowing for an exhaustive evaluation as the model learns.

2.4 Evaluation metrics

Commonly, in generative music tasks, evaluation is done through subjective listening tests. It makes sense since the ultimate consumer of a creative system's output is a human subject. However, an objective evaluation could help with reproducibility and comparability of results across research projects.

In [25], this topic is discussed at length and an alternative evaluation method for creative tasks is proposed. The approach suggested consists in extracting features from the expected outputs (ground truths from the original dataset) and the predicted outputs and calculating Probability Distribution Functions (PDFs), means and standard deviations in order to compute feature distances inter and intra-datasets.

In this project a somewhat hybrid evaluation is carried out: the quality of the generated drum patterns is assessed by a combination of informal listening checks, visual inspection of piano rolls and plots, but also the PDFs of several features are extracted for the predicted and expected outputs, using a simplified approach of the method proposed in [25] (see Figure 2.5).

Furthermore, a visual representation called *velocity heatmap* is computed. In this representation, all beat examples for each voice and genre of a specific subset (e.g. test set ground truths) are plotted in the same time axis, as shown in Figure 2.6. Velocity is represented along the y axis, and dark red color clusters represent hit density. This graphs illustrate patterns characteristic of each genre and voice, making it possible to visually compare between ground truths and predictions.

Figure 2.5: Feature extraction and PDF calculation from ground truths and predictions.

Figure 2.6: Velocity heatmap example

Feature PDFs, velocity heatmaps and loss values will be computed⁴ and used to draw conclusions on the results of the experiments carried out, and together with our subjective listening of generated audios, the best runs of a W&B sweep will be selected and discussed.

⁴These calculations are performed with the GrooveEvaluator. <https://github.com/behzadhi/GrooveEvaluator>

Chapter 3

Results and evaluation

In this chapter, the experiments that have been carried out will be described, together with the issues encountered along the way, the decisions taken to overcome these and the final evaluation of a set of selected trained models, comparing them to our baseline (GrooVAE, the Seq2Seq model used in [1]). In Appendix A you can find links to all of our Weight & Biases reports, containing interactive plots and audio examples.

3.1 Initial sweep¹

The first successful sweep tracked with W&B (which can be found [here](#)²) has 27 completed runs, each of them training the model for 100 epochs³. Training time varies depending on the combination of hyperparameters, ranging from 20 minutes to around 2 hours per run.

An overview of the hyperparameters of each run with respect to the training loss is displayed in Figure 3.1. In order to do an initial assessment of whether the model is

¹A Weights&Biases report detailing this section, with audios and interactive graphs can be found at https://wandb.ai/mmil_tap2drum/transformer_groove_tap2drum/reports/First-sweeps-and-lack-of-variation-in-offsets--Vmlldzo5NzgyMjI

²https://wandb.ai/mmil_tap2drum/transformer_groove_tap2drum/sweeps/79ezpikb

³All trainings are run in a High-Performance Computing (HPC) cluster, using 4 CPUs with a total pool of 24 GB CPU memory and Tesla T4 16GB GPUs.

working as expected or any major adjustments need to be made, some of the models are briefly examined.

Figure 3.1: Initial sweep with 27 runs - each of these lines represents a run with a different set of hyperparameters

After an initial listen to the [synthesized audios](#)⁴ corresponding to the test subset, we believe the model is doing a good enough job at replicating the ground truth’s *groove* in the predictions - albeit we suspect it might be overfitting. Figure 3.2 shows the piano rolls of one of the predicted patterns.

The velocity heatmaps (explained in Section 2.4) reveal, however, an issue in the generation of microtimings or offsets. As can be seen in Figure 3.3, the scatter points of the predictions are all lying densely on the grid lines, meaning the offset values are very close to 0. Observing these plots, our intuition is that the model is learning to predict hits and velocities better than offsets.

3.1.1 Offset variability

Upon observing the hit loss, velocity loss and offset loss values of several runs, like the one shown in Figure 3.4, we believe that the lack of offset variability might be related to the proportions of these values in the total loss calculation. For example, at the end of this run, the hit loss value is approximately 2, the velocity loss 0.25 and the offset loss 0.05. This means the offset loss only accounts for around 2.18% of the total loss value at the end of the run in this case.

⁴https://wandb.ai/mmil_tap2drum/transformer_groove_tap2drum/reports/Test-set-g-t-vs-predictions-7ecgdrhn---Vmlldzo5NzgxMzI

Figure 3.2: Piano roll of a prediction generated in run [northern-sweep-26](#)

Figure 3.3: Velocity heatmaps of run [northern-sweep-26](#) for three genres, comparing ground truths (above) and predictions (below).

Figure 3.4: Individual training losses over 100 epochs of run `northern-sweep-26`

Multiple experiments were run in an effort to fix this issue⁵, trying to balance the individual losses and applying scaling factors and divisors in several different ways. Several of these experiments failed, generating worse results and some of them even predicting all-empty patterns for most cases. Part of the reason causing these failures may also be the hyperparameters chosen for each experiment, making us suspect that the model is slightly *fragile* in this sense: for certain configurations it predicts only empty patterns.

Of all the experiments attempted, the one we consider to be most promising involves adding a *penalty* factor or loss multiplier (p in Equation 2.2). This factor multiplies the hit, velocity and offset losses where the ground truth hits are 0, giving less importance to the places where there are no expected hits. Equation 3.1 shows an example (reduced to 4 voices, 3 timesteps) of this calculation. The same \mathbf{P} matrix is used for the losses of the velocities and offsets. We believe that this helps the model learn *faster* where it should create hits, and therefore everything else, including offsets, might be learned better.

To this end, a new [hyperparameter sweep](#)⁶ was then conducted with this adjustment, resulting in some of the runs showing a great deal of offset variability in comparison to the first experiment. Figure 3.5 shows the kick velocity heatmaps for the test set of one of the runs of this sweep, and comparing the predictions to those of Figure

⁵A Weights&Biases report detailing this section can be found at https://wandb.ai/mmil_tap2drum/transformer_groove_tap2drum/reports/First-sweeps-and-lack-of-variation-in-offsets--Vmlldzo5NzgyMjI

⁶https://wandb.ai/mmil_tap2drum/transformer_groove_tap2drum/sweeps/j9r6pt0s

3.3, we can observe offsets are now more varied and not all hits lie exactly on the grid lines.

$$\begin{aligned}
 BCE(\mathbf{H}_{\text{predicted}}, \mathbf{H}_{\text{expected}}) &= \begin{pmatrix} 0.52 & 0.10 & 0.27 & 0.32 \\ 0.74 & 0.52 & 0.14 & 0.32 \\ 0.64 & 0.60 & 0.30 & 0.34 \end{pmatrix} \\
 p = 0.5, \mathbf{H}_{\text{expected}} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \Rightarrow \mathbf{P} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0.5 & 1 & 0.5 \\ 0.5 & 0.5 & 0.5 & 0.5 \\ 0.5 & 1 & 1 & 0.5 \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.1) \\
 \text{hit loss} = \sum_{i,j} (\mathbf{P} \circ BCE(\mathbf{H}_p, \mathbf{H}_e))_{i,j} = \sum \begin{pmatrix} 0.52 & 0.05 & 0.27 & 0.16 \\ 0.37 & 0.26 & 0.07 & 0.16 \\ 0.32 & 0.60 & 0.30 & 0.17 \end{pmatrix} = 3.25
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 3.5: Velocity heatmaps of run `warm-sweep-32` for three genres, comparing ground truths (above) and predictions (below).

3.2 Model selection⁷

To evaluate and compare our model with GrooVAE [1](our baseline), first we must select the best possible hyperparameter configuration from the [latest sweep](#)⁸. The test subset will be used for this selection process, as these examples have not been used for training and our model has not *seen* them before.

Since each run uses a different p or loss multiplier, loss values are not directly comparable. For example, let’s take a look at two runs with different loss values for the test set: [absurd-sweep-24](#) and [lyric-sweep-12](#) with test losses of 0.04 and 1.18 respectively (Figure 3.6).

Figure 3.6: Sweep [j9r6pt0s](#), highlighting runs [lyric-sweep-12](#) and [absurd-sweep-24](#)

A lower loss value could lead us to believe that [absurd-sweep-24](#) is the better model of the two. Nonetheless, as shown in Figure 3.7b, this run generates completely saturated predictions (all timesteps and voices have their hits set to 1). On the other hand, [lyric-sweep-12](#), with a higher test loss value, generates predictions that are closer to the ground truth (see Figure 3.7). Since the loss values cannot be used to narrow down the best configurations, we considered other metrics.

Hit accuracy (Correctly predicted hits/Total predicted hits) tells us the percentage of correctly predicted hits. For the two runs discussed above, [absurd-sweep-24](#) and

⁷A Weights&Biases report about this section with audios and interactive graphs can be found at https://wandb.ai/mmil_tap2drum/transformer_groove_tap2drum/reports/Selecting-the-best-models--Vmlldzo5NzgxNjY

⁸https://wandb.ai/mmil_tap2drum/transformer_groove_tap2drum/sweeps/j9r6pt0s

Figure 3.7: Example ground truth and predictions, [absurd-sweep-24](#) vs [lyric-sweep-12](#)

[lyric-sweep-12](#), the test hit accuracies reported on the last epoch are 12.14% and 90.38% respectively, so we believe this metric can help us narrow down model selection.

Since our baseline, the GrooVAE model (evaluated [here](#)⁹), has a hit accuracy over the test subset of 87.42%, we selected the runs with over 88% test hit accuracy. That leaves us with 12 hyperparameter configuration candidates. In order to further reduce our selection, the 4 runs out of those 12 with lowest offset loss are chosen, in an attempt to improve offset variability.

Figure 3.8 shows the hyperparameters of the selected runs, together with the offset loss and hit accuracy values over the test set. As the rest of runs in the sweep, these models have been trained for 100 epochs (no stop condition has been implemented). And considering we are not using a step scheduler during training, the learning rate is constant throughout epochs. This means we also need to consider for how long each of these models should be trained: if they are not trained long enough they might underfit, but if they are trained for too long, they might learn the training

⁹https://wandb.ai/mmil_tap2drum/transformer_groove_tap2drum/runs/zc69p7e3

Figure 3.8: Selected runs for further evaluation

subset too well and not be able to generalize (overfitting). To avoid this, we apply the regularization method known as *early stopping*, described in [26], on the four selected hyperparameter configurations.

The four selected models are then re-trained, and the optimal epoch for each run is selected looking at the test loss slope and the minimal distance between training and test loss, as shown in Figure 3.9.

Figure 3.9: Loss of training set and test set (smoothed with exponential running average) of the four selected and re-trained models

As a result, the models chosen for evaluation are:

- [rosy-durian-248](#), epoch 26
- [misunderstood-bush-246](#), epoch 26
- [solar-shadow-247](#), epoch 41
- [hopeful-gorge-252](#), epoch 90

The hyperparameters of the selected models are shown in Table 3.1.

Model	batch size	d model	dim feedfw	dropout	learning rate	n heads	n layers	loss mult
rosy-durian	16	512	16	0.1093	0.0388	4	6	0.53
misunderstood-bush	16	128	128	0.1038	0.0363	4	11	0.27
solar-shadow	16	128	16	0.1594	0.0367	1	7	0.49
hopeful-gorge	16	512	64	0.1708	0.0071	4	8	0.33

Table 3.1: Hyperparameter configurations selected

3.3 Evaluation

The selected models are evaluated over the validation subset, given that the test set has been used for hyperparameter tuning. For the sake of comparing these models to our baseline, the tapped sequences from the validation set have also been used to generate predictions with the GrooVAE Tap2Drum model [1] and these metrics have been logged to a [W&B run](#)¹⁰.

Accuracy and MSE

The overall hit accuracies of the four selected models over the validation subset are higher than GrooVAE’s (Table 3.2). The best model by this metric is [rosy-durian-248](#), with 91.20% accuracy, 3.33% higher than that of GrooVAE’s.

Model	Hit Accuracy
rosy-durian-248	91.20%
misunderstood-bush-246	88.15%
solar-shadow-247	90.56%
hopeful-gorge-252	89.07%
GrooVAE	87.87%

Table 3.2: Hit accuracy of the selected models vs GrooVAE, validation subset

¹⁰https://wandb.ai/mmil_tap2drum/transformer_groove_tap2drum/runs/zc69p7e3

Figure 3.10 shows the validation hit accuracy per voice of two of the selected models, as it evolves during training. Next to each subplot, the GrooVAE hit accuracy is represented with bars (only one value is plotted since we have not re-trained the model).

(a) `misunderstood-bush-246` vs GrooVAE

(b) `hopeful-gorge-252` vs GrooVAE

Figure 3.10: Hit accuracy per voice over validation subset

In both Figure 3.10a and 3.10b the final accuracy values are very similar to those of GrooVAE. This makes sense since the overall hit accuracy of these two models is only 0.28% and 1.2% above GrooVAE's (Table 3.2). If we were only looking at the final values, we might get the impression that the toms, the open hi-hat and the crash are the voices that are learned *better* because they have higher accuracy. Nevertheless, looking at the temporal evolution of the individual voices, we can see

that for four of the voices (kick, snare, closed hi-hat and ride), the accuracy values vary as the model learns, whereas for the rest they remain mostly constant. This suggests there are fewer hits for the toms, open hat and crash in the GMD dataset, and we suspect that for this reason the model generates very few hits (if any) for these voices. Therefore, the high accuracy values for some of the voices might just mean there are almost no hits neither in the ground truths nor in the predictions.

Figure 3.11

Figure 3.12: Velocity MSE per voice over validation subset, [solar-shadow-247](#) vs GrooVAE

Figure 3.13: Offset (μ timing) MSE per voice over validation subset, [rosy-durian-248](#) vs GrooVAE

The velocity and offset MSEs (Figures 3.12 and 3.13) are similar across all four selected models. Like with the hit accuracy, the velocity MSE values vary over time

for the kick, snare, closed hat and ride as the model learns. For the offset MSE values, a similar thing happens but this time only three of those four voices seem to improve over time: kick, snare and closed hat. The ride voice’s offset MSE, on the other hand, stays almost constant over time. Our intuition is that this could be again related to the linear combination of losses, where the offset loss is much smaller than the hit loss (Figure 3.4) resulting in the model learning offsets not as *well* as hits or velocities.

Both for the velocity and offset MSE, it seems like the error values of our model are somewhat smaller than for GrooVAE, especially for those voices where the MSE drops as the model learns. The loss calculation in GrooVAE is done in the same way as our models, except for the loss multiplier explained in subsection 3.1.1. We believe that introducing this factor might be what is helping our models learn velocities and offsets slightly better than GrooVAE.

Synthesized audios and velocity heatmaps

We listened to the synthesized audios corresponding to our models’ predictions for the validation subset (you can listen to them [here](#)¹¹). It is our impression that the drum patterns predicted by [rosy-durian-248](#) and [misunderstood-bush-246](#) seem to sound closer to the ground truth patterns than the other two models. To our ears, the GrooVAE predictions sound simpler than our models’ predictions.

Another interesting observation from our personal listening evaluations is that for those genres that typically have simpler, uniformly accented patterns (rock, punk, pop), the predicted beats sound closer to the ground truths than for those genres that frequently use *more complex* patterns (jazz, funk).

Even though we are using the validation subset for evaluation, we also listened to predictions from the training and test subsets. Something interesting we noticed was that there are some patterns with a few triplets in the test funk beats, and that the predictions for these sound further from the ground truths than most of

¹¹https://wandb.ai/mmil_tap2drum/transformer_groove_tap2drum/reports/Audios-selected-models-vs-GrooVAE--Vmlldzo5NzgxNzU

the other generated patterns ([here](#)¹² are a couple of examples). We think that this might be related to the fact that we are only using examples with 4/4 time signature and converting them to a 16th note resolution in our preprocessing steps (going from MIDI to HVO).

(a) rosy-durian-248

(b) GrooVAE

Figure 3.14: Velocity heatmaps per genre for snare voice over validation subset. Ground truth vs predictions

The velocity heatmaps of our models’ predictions along with GrooVAE’s can be found in [this W&B report](#)¹³. Figure 3.14 illustrates the velocity heatmaps for the snare drum predictions of [rosy-durian-248](#) and [GrooVAE](#). The ground truth patterns of rock, punk, hip-hop and funk for this subset look quite similar to us: snares on the 2nd, 4th, 6th and 8th beat. The predictions for these genres, both by our models

¹²https://wandb.ai/mmil_tap2drum/transformer_groove_tap2drum/reports/Triplets-in-patterns--Vmlldzo5NzgxNjE

¹³https://wandb.ai/mmil_tap2drum/transformer_groove_tap2drum/reports/Velocity-heatmaps-selected-models-vs-GrooVAE--Vmlldzo5NzgxNzA

and GrooVAE, seem quite close to the corresponding ground truths. We believe that these genre similarities help to compensate the low representation of some of these genres in the GMD dataset (e.g. hip-hop), making it easier for the model to predict beats resembling the ground truths.

This [other report](#)¹⁴ shows an overview of the velocity heatmaps as they evolve during training. In it we can see that the five less frequent voices (the three toms, the crash and open hi-hat), tend to start generating hits in the last few epochs of each run, consistent with what we discussed about Figure 3.10. Besides, in these animations, it seems like when the models start generating a voice, the first hits appear closer to the grid lines and all at the same velocity, and as training advances, they start moving away from the gridlines and start expanding vertically (different velocity values). We believe this is related to the proportions of the individual loss values within the total loss (see Figure 3.4), as from what we can tell, the models learn to improve the generated hits, velocities in offsets in that order.

Probability Distribution Functions of extracted features

From all the predictions of the validation subset, some features are extracted and their Probability Distribution Functions (PDFs) computed (as illustrated in Figure 2.5).

One of these features is Number of Instruments (NoI), which simply accounts for the number of active voices in a pattern (those that have at least one hit in said pattern). The PDFs of this feature are shown in Figure 3.15. The mean of the ground truth PDF of all genres combined is 4.26, its standard deviation 1.27, and a significant peak can be observed at 4 voices/instruments. We thought this was interesting because it seems to reinforce what we suspected by observing the accuracies and MSEs over training, i.e., in the GMD dataset quite a few of the drum patterns are played with only 3 to 5 voices. Both our model's and GrooVAE's combined PDFs have a lower standard deviation, which might indicate that the predictions have

¹⁴https://wandb.ai/mmil_tap2drum/transformer_groove_tap2drum/reports/Evolution-of-velocity-heatmaps-during-training-validation-set---Vmlldzo5NzkkMzI

more patterns with exactly 4 voices compared to the ground truths.

Figure 3.15: NoI - PDFs per genre over validation subset. Ground truths vs [rosy-durian-248](#) vs [GrooVAE](#)

The velocity similarity score feature (Figure 3.16) informs about the symmetry of the drum patterns, dividing them in two and comparing the first halves with the second halves. Comparing the mean and standard deviation values of ground truth PDFs and both our model’s and GrooVAE’s PDFs, we notice these values are quite similar across genres and models. We believe this indicates that both models learned that there are some similarities and/or patterns repeating between the first and second bars of each example.

Another potentially interesting feature is the complexity of a pattern. This feature reflects how complex the patterns are in terms of rhythm (syncopation) and density

Figure 3.16: Velocity similarity score - PDFs per genre over validation subset. Ground truths vs *rosy-durian-248* vs *GrooVAE*

of hits. The PDFs shown in Figure 3.17 confirm some intuitions we have about the beats we listened to from different genres. E.g. we perceived hip hop, punk and pop examples to be simpler than latin, funk or jazz ones across ground truths and predictions, and the mean values of these PDFs support this impression. In any case, it seems that the mean complexity of the predicted patterns of both our model and *GrooVAE* are close to the ground truth mean values, meaning both models seem capable of reproducing complexity.

Lastly, a feature called microtiming accuracy, understood as the absolute sum of

Figure 3.17: Complexity - PDFs per genre over validation subset. Ground truths vs [rosy-durian-248](#) vs [GrooVAE](#)

microtiming deviations on 8th note positions, is extracted. Microtiming accuracy can give us an idea of the overall absolute values of offsets. One of the issues we tried to overcome, as explained in subsection 3.1.1, was the lack of variability in offsets, being the hits too close to the grid lines in many predictions. The microtiming accuracy PDFs displayed in Figure 3.18 show clearly that this issue is still present. Most of the mean values for the predicted sets are half of the corresponding ground truth mean values, possibly meaning that most of the predicted offsets are still closer to the grid lines than the ground truth offsets.

In a nutshell, the predictions of the selected models can compete with those from our baseline according to the hit accuracy, velocity and offset MSE metrics, and in our subjective opinion, the generated beats sound really promising. However, we

Figure 3.18: Microtiming accuracy - PDFs per genre over validation subset. Ground truths vs *rosy-durian-248* vs *GrooVAE*

cannot claim that our model is undeniably *better* than GrooVAE: it's ultimately up to the final user to decide which of these models would be most useful creatively.

Chapter 4

Discussion

In this chapter, the main outcomes and limitations of this project are discussed, along with possible future experiments and some conclusions.

4.1 General discussion

The evaluation carried out in the previous chapter shows that the Transformer Groove model is able to predict full drum beats from tapped sequences, generating, in our opinion, decent drum patterns. According to some of the metrics computed, it seems like our model is, at the very least, at the same level as our baseline (e.g. the validation hit accuracy of our best model is 3.33% higher than GrooVAE's). Listening to the generated patterns, we get a general impression that GrooVAE's predicted patterns sound simpler than our models', this is however completely subjective.

The success of our model (or that it *works*, so to speak) is proof that tokenization is not essential for symbolic music generation when training a Transformer-based architecture. In all our experiments, we fed the models with data in a format called HVO (explained in subsection 2.1.1). This format is a direct embedding, meaning the model does not have to transform the data or learn how to tokenize it, the data is already in a format that both the model and we can understand. Transformers traditionally use tokenization, and they are known to be data-hungry models, but

perhaps because our models don't need to learn this extra task, they might not need as much data.

4.2 Limitations and future work

One of the biggest struggles we dealt with in this master thesis was the lack of offset variability. We strongly believe the root of this issue is in the linear combination of individual losses, and although a new hyperparameter was introduced the problem is not completely gone. A possible future experiment could consist on splitting the model into three parallel networks, one for hits, another one for velocities, and the third one for offsets, learning these somewhat separately, or adding an extra layer that would learn how to combine the three individual losses.

In the evaluation we have carried out we compare the generated patterns against *expected* results, but because the end goal of the system is a creative task, in a real-world application of this project, there would not be such a thing as a correct prediction or an incorrect one. Our model is deterministic: it generates a set of probabilities that is always the same for a specific input, which might not be very exciting if the user wants to listen to several possible outcomes. A way to introduce some randomness is to use a probability distribution for hit activation, generating a matrix of random probabilities that is the same size as the predicted hits, then generating a hit if the predicted probability is higher than the corresponding random one. This has been implemented in our repository, although it hasn't been discussed in this report. If these models were to be integrated in a product, adding more options could be interesting for the users, like being able to condition what voices will be used in the generated patterns or what genre these new beats should resemble.

The size of the GMD dataset is relatively small, and the 2-measure examples used are fragments of longer performances, so many patterns resemble one another. Moreover, only 4/4 time signature patterns are used, further limiting our dataset. Using a different dataset would help us understand better the ability of our models to generalize. Other ways of *tappifying* the ground truth sequences might also provide

some insights about how this task can help users in their creative process. For example, taking the ground truth patterns of the GMD and ask a diverse group of people to tap along these beats, then using these tapped sequences as inputs. This would increase the size of the dataset since we would have several possible inputs for the same output, and would probably be a good approach if the final user is expected to tap on a button or screen to generate the inputs. Another potential way of generating the inputs could be to use a multi-instrument dataset and *tappify* the melodies played by other instruments, like the guitar or the bass. This could perhaps be useful if the final user is a guitarist or a bassist that wants to generate a beat that goes with their compositions.

4.3 Conclusion

Our model, a Transformer encoder-only architecture trained over the GMD, can perform the Tap2Drum task to what we consider, from our evaluation, a satisfactory degree. It can replicate the *expected outcomes* for a given tapped sequence. However, the ultimate goal of Tap2Drum is to be used for creative purposes: in order to assess how useful our model would be in a creative process, it needs to be put in the hand of music creators, only then would our evaluation be doubtlessly complete.

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Appendix A

Repositories and reports

Code repositories

- TransformerGrooveTap2Drum GitHub repository
<https://github.com/marinaniet0/TransformerGrooveTap2Drum>
 - Google Colab notebook to try out some of our trained models
https://github.com/marinaniet0/TransformerGrooveTap2Drum/blob/main/Transformer_Groove_Tap2Drum_Demo.ipynb

Weights and Biases

- Transformer Groove Tap2Drum project, in this project you will find all the sweeps and runs from the experiments carried out.
https://wandb.ai/mmil_tap2drum/transformer_groove_tap2drum
- Reports:
 - First sweep and experiments to try and fix the lack of offset variability
https://wandb.ai/mmil_tap2drum/transformer_groove_tap2drum/reports/First-sweeps-and-lack-of-variation-in-offsets--Vmlldzo5NzgyMjI
 - Model selection
https://wandb.ai/mmil_tap2drum/transformer_groove_tap2drum/reports/Selecting-the-best-models--Vmlldzo5NzgxNjY

- Velocity heatmaps of selected models vs GrooVAE
https://wandb.ai/mmil_tap2drum/transformer_groove_tap2drum/reports/Velocity-heatmaps-selected-models-vs-GrooVAE--Vmlldzo5NzgxNzA
- Synthesized audios of selected models vs GrooVAE
https://wandb.ai/mmil_tap2drum/transformer_groove_tap2drum/reports/Audios-selected-models-vs-GrooVAE--Vmlldzo5NzgxNzU
- Evolution of heatmaps during training
https://wandb.ai/mmil_tap2drum/transformer_groove_tap2drum/reports/Evolution-of-velocity-heatmaps-during-training-validation-set---Vmlldzo5NzkxMzI